

PILOTING INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN CONFESSIONAL SCHOOLS: A CASE STUDY OF THE CAMEROON BAPTIST CONVENTION EDUCATION DEPARTMENT

Atanga, Naphalin A.

University of Bamenda, Cameroon/Cameroon Baptist Convention, Bamenda, Cameroon
naatanga2008@yahoo.com

and

Indi, Nyanganji Job

Cameroon Baptist Convention, Bamenda, Cameroon
nyanganjjin@yahoo.com

The Cameroon Baptist Convention Education Department (CBCED), in collaboration with the CBC Health Services and Liliane Foundation, introduced the Sustainable Inclusive Education Project (SIEP) in its school system in 2018. This was in response to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal number four "ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all." The CBCED piloted SIEP in seven schools from 2018-2020. All learners in these schools were screened annually using a multidisciplinary medical team to identify different types of impairments. Community-Based Rehabilitation staff were trained annually for three years to mobilize and encourage parents having Children With Disabilities (CWD) to send them to school. The CBCED gave all CWDs enrolled in SIEP pilot schools an annual 10% discount on tuition. In addition, monthly cash support of 50,000 FCFA was given for two years to seven CWDs. Teachers (145) were trained twice a year for three years to build their capacities on inclusive teaching strategies and some teachers were trained exclusively in Braille (21) and American Sign Language (15). Enrolment of CWDs into SIEP pilot schools has been on the increase since 2018 (19 in 2018/2019, 151 in 2019/2020, 301 in 2020/2021 and 378 in 2021/2022). Academic performance of all learners in SIEP pilot schools has also improved since 2018 (11.7 in 2018/2019, 13.3 in 2019/2020, 14.3 in 2020/2021 and 14.5 in 2021/2022), an indication that focusing on Inclusive Education is more profitable and productive to all learners. The CBCED intends to extend the focus on inclusive education to all its secondary and primary schools as well as to other confessional schools in Cameroon.

Key Words: Inclusive education; Inclusive teaching strategies; Impairments

Introduction

The Cameroon Baptist Convention Education Department (CBCED) is one of the departments of the Cameroon Baptist Convention (CBC), a confessional organization in Cameroon. The CBCED provides education to all citizens in partnership with the Cameroon government in line with its mission statement:

"The Cameroon Baptist Convention Education Department in collaboration with the Cameroon Government and in fulfillment of the command of the Lord Jesus Christ in Mathew 28:19-20, seeks to provide sound quality Christian education as an expression of love and concern and as a means of witnessing in order that the beneficiaries might be brought to God through Jesus Christ."

This mission statement led to the vision statement: "The vision of the Education Department of the Cameroon Baptist Convention is to provide Inclusive Sound Quality Christian Education through excellence in academics, high moral rectitude, discipleship, quality personnel, state-of-the-art infrastructure, and welfare of staff and learners."

The CBCED reflected on its mission and vision statements, reviewing same through the lens of the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDG4), "Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning

opportunities for all." (This reflection revealed that although the CBCED has successfully provided education to citizens in Cameroon over the years, this has not been inclusive enough to accommodate learners with disabilities. Learners with impairments who made their way into the CBCED school system over the years and were unable to overcome challenges they encountered lacked the needed support to enhance their learning. These learners often drop out and many of them sometimes stop going to school because their parents are discouraged. As a major provider of education in Cameroon, leaving out children with disabilities or not providing adequate support to them when they come to school can be seen as a big shortcoming on the part of the church and also falling short of expressing God's love to all created in His image. Seeing that as a church, we ought to "encourage one another and build each other up" (1 Thessalonians 5: 11), the CBCED redefined its purpose to make the inclusive component more active.

In partnership with the Cameroon Baptist Convention Health Services (CBCHS) and the Liliane Foundation (LF) of the Netherlands, the CBCED piloted the Sustainable Inclusive Education Project (SIEP) in seven (five Primary Schools, one Secondary School and one Teacher Training College) of its schools from January 2018 to December 2020. The goal of SIEP is to contribute to development by supporting the government of Cameroon in the provision of quality inclusive education. The overall objective of SIEP is: to achieve an inclusive education system that can respond to the diverse needs of all pupils/students within the framework of universal learning design. We define an Inclusive Education (IE) system as one that includes, and meets the needs of all, including those with special educational needs, whatever their gender, life circumstances, health, disability, stage of development, capacity to learn, level of achievement, financial or any other circumstances. Having tried IE this time, we have gained some exciting experiences, realized some benefits of it, and also encountered some challenges that need to be overcome so that we forge ahead in supporting all learners.

The focus of this paper is to share our experiences in implementing IE from 2018 to 2020, three years. The first part of this paper will explain the activities of SIEP and the outcome. The second part of this paper will also explain our walk alone as CBCED in the implementation of inclusive education. The third part will project what we intend to do and achieve in the future to have all CBCED schools implement inclusive education and also extend to other confessional school systems.

Implementing IE from January 2018 - December 2020

During this period, SIEP's overall objectives stated above had specific objectives. Two of the specific objectives are: to institutionalize inclusion in the Baptist Education system and to increase access to quality inclusive education for children with disabilities. Several activities were carried out to realize these specific objectives. We believe that in carrying out these activities, the specific objectives will be met and hence the overall objective will be realized, leading to the achievement of the project goal as shown in Figure 1 below.

Specific objective 1: To institutionalize inclusion in the Baptist Education system

This specific objective is intended to have all schools of the CBCED operate IE so as to provide access to all learners with disabilities. The following activities were engaged to achieve this objective: Strengthen and widen in-service training for teaching staff, Mainstream disability in teacher training, Introduce transition programs, and remodel current infrastructures to improve access to built-up areas. These are explained as follows.

Strengthen and widen in-service training for teaching staff. In this activity, all teachers of the seven schools mentioned above were trained twice a year. First, all administrators of these schools were trained on attitude change and the need to accommodate all learners. This training led these administrators to see the need to modify their enrolment forms so that other learners can have access to them. For example, admission forms are now in Braille so that learners with vision impairments and knowledge in Braille can complete them on their own. For learners with hearing impairment, sign language personnel were then co-opted to assist them complete their admission forms.

Figure 1: Diagrammatic Flow from project activities to project goals

In each specific goal, we now explain the specific activities that were carried out:

Second, all classroom teachers were trained on inclusive pedagogic practices twice a year for three years. Each training session lasted three days so we had six days in a year to equip teachers with IE resources. Topics for these IE trainings over the three year period included Understanding the Needs of Learners with Impairments and Participation Restrictions, Designing Individual Education Plans (IEP), Differentiating Instruction, Multiple Intelligences, Universal Design: Planning a lesson to include Learners with disability, Transitioning from Primary to Secondary School and from one class to another: What Teachers Should Know, Teaching Mathematics to students with impairments, Teaching Physics to students with impairments, Teaching English Language to students with impairments, Types of Orthopaedic Impairments and Possible Classroom Challenges, Assessments For Effective Inclusion: Why and How, Strategies for Including Learners with Orthopaedic impairments in Teaching/Learning Practices, Drawing up Lesson Plans Inclusive of Learners with Orthopaedic impairments, Understanding and Including Learners with Specific Learning Disabilities in the Classroom, Understanding and Including Learners with Intellectual Disabilities in the Classroom, Understanding and Including Learners with Emotional and Behavioural Disorders in the Classroom, Responding to Teachers Challenges in Relation to Inclusive Teaching and Learning. In addition to these, teachers participating in these trainings always prepare lessons and micro-teach their peers and receive feedback from their peers on what needs to be added or subtracted to make the lesson meet the needs of the specific disability under consideration.

Mainstream disability in teacher training. This component was intended for the CBCED to analyze the curriculum being used to train teachers to teach primary school learners. Upon close examination of the curriculum, we discovered that there is an underlying assumption that drives teacher training programs in Cameroon. The curriculum is built on the assumption that those who show up to be trained as teachers for primary school are grounded in content. That means they are knowledgeable enough in all fields that are seen as needed for primary school pupils. As such, what they need in teacher training schools is how to teach. So, the training focus in teacher training colleges in Cameroon is on the pedagogy or teaching methods that pre-service teachers are supposed to experience and acquire. This makes teacher trainers ignore content and focus on teaching strategies.

We approached the Regional Delegates and proposed that teacher training needs to focus on both content and teaching strategies. With attention being drawn to content, we intended to examine how learners with some impairments can be taught to access those concepts in the different subject areas. Our Regional Delegates responded that only the state has the authority to modify the curriculum of the teacher training program in Cameroon. This caused us to abandon that path and thus included American Sign Language (ASL) and Braille as part of our training and the teacher training school. It is worth noting that these two are introduced as additional skills that those who attend the Baptist Teacher Training College (BTTC) Ndop acquire.

Introduce transition programs. Many children with disabilities (CWD) who come to our SIEP pilot schools do come directly from home and lack some norms and skills. For example, those coming from home with hearing impairments (HI) might have learned to communicate using local or traditional signs which might be different from the signs used in school. Such children are not taken directly into mainstream classrooms as they might be even more confused. A program is designed to bridge the gap between home and school for them so that their inclusion in mainstream classrooms can be smooth. During this time, the learner is taught standard ASL that would be used in the classroom to teach. In addition, learners with vision impairments (VI) are not taken directly to class. Before inclusion into mainstream classrooms is done, these children are taught orientation and mobility skills. They are also taught how to use the white cane and communicate with it. Since they have VI, they are taught how to write and read Braille.

Furthermore, since many of these CWDs were abandoned at home for too long all alone as others went to school or went about their businesses, this loneliness may have developed bitterness in them, causing them to react violently with other people. Such attitudes need to be diffused and dealt with and replaced with love. Love is taught to these children at school. We observe to see that they are ready for mainstream classrooms before they are included in there. Also, these children need to access school facilities such as toilets and bathrooms on their own. They are taught to do so, beginning with support and then withdrawing such support to ensure that a certain level of independence has been attained. When our staff is satisfied with the progress of each child with a disability, then such a child is included in mainstream classrooms. This period of transition from home to school can take between six months and one academic year.

Lastly, the transition is not only from home to school but also from one class to another within the same school and also from one school to another. In our primary schools, one teacher teaches all the subjects for each class. They own a classroom and are responsible for all the learners in that classroom. If CWDs are promoted from one class to another, the sending and receiving teachers meet together and discuss each case. The receiving teacher is briefed by the sending teacher on the strengths, weaknesses, challenges, and support system that each child needs. If they need preferential seating positions, that is discussed too. This is done so that the receiving teacher's mind is prepared for the learner and reasonable accommodation is made before the start of the new academic year. From one school to another might be from the CBC Primary School, Nkwen to the Baptist Comprehensive High School (BCHS), Nkwen in the same complex. Since these two schools are in the same complex, the Head Teacher of the Primary School discusses the case of each child as mentioned above with the administration of BCHS Nkwen and also hands a copy of the learner's file to the principal. The administration of BCHS Nkwen also convenes a meeting with all teachers in the new class and new school to discuss the same with them. In this way, each learner with a disability is carefully monitored and handed over from one level to another. If a learner with impairment is coming from another school with no such record, our staff assess their situation on a one-to-one basis to determine what they need before accessing our mainstream classrooms. Suppose a learner with impairment leaves our schools and goes to another school, the information is held in our files and shared when requested so that the learners can be adequately supported in their new learning environments.

Remodel current infrastructures to improve access to built-up areas. Before 2018, our infrastructures were such that learners with VI had difficulties accessing them. Similarly, learners in wheelchairs can't just have access to. In addition, our toilets were such that learners in wheelchairs and with orthopedic impairments had great challenges accessing them. Our buildings were remodeled to include ramps so that those on wheelchairs can easily have access to mainstream classrooms as shown in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Ramp for CWDs to gain access to their classrooms

The doors of each of the classrooms were also made bigger to make provision for those on wheelchairs to move in as shown in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3: Classroom doors wide enough for learners on wheelchairs to enter

The chalkboards that were initially very high up were brought lower so that learners could be called upon to write on the board. Each classroom has a small ramp for learners on wheelchairs to move up and write their ideas in a classroom discussion as shown in Figure 4 below.

Figure 4: Short ramps in classrooms to enable learners on wheelchairs do their presentations

This pattern of construction is now the norm in the CBC Education Department. Any new construction must include ramps and specifications for toilets and classroom doors followed so that CWDs are welcomed. This is so that we are adequately preparing to receive learners with impairments rather than wait until they arrive and we start thinking of what to do.

In SIEP pilot schools we are still trying to do more. Another objective of the project is to have learners with impairments come to school and receive quality inclusive education. We do this in several ways as illustrated next.

Specific objective 2: To increase access to quality inclusive education for children with disabilities

This objective is aimed at encouraging learners with disabilities from diverse backgrounds to come to school and receive quality inclusive education. The following activities were implemented to realize this: advocate for the CBC Education Board to provide a 5% school fee waiver for CWDs, screen children in schools and communities for impairment, provide conditional cash transfers to parents of children with disabilities, undertake routine supervision, and creation/functioning of resource center and rooms. We now explain what each of these means in the project.

Advocate for the CBC Education Board to provide a 5% school fee waiver for CWDs.

The intent here is to subsidize fee payment so that parents take advantage of this and send their children with disabilities to school. It is worth noting here that the government of Cameroon is implementing as a policy, tuition-free education for CWDs in public schools. However, in our CBC Education Department, school fees are the main source of income so we could pay teachers and other staff members. As such, the tuition fee is part of the expenses for CWDs. The Sustainable Inclusive Education Project (SIEP) advocated that the CBC Education Board institute a 5% tuition fee waiver for CWDs. The CBC Education Board actually approved a 10% tuition fee waiver for all CWDs in SIEP pilot schools. The good news is that this advocacy yielded much fruit and has increased the number of CWDs accessing SIEP pilot schools from 19 in 2018/2019 to 151 in 2019/2020 to 301 in 2020/2021 and then 378 in 2021/2022. Because these CWDs have been at home with no medical attention or support in most of the cases, when they come to school, we screen them to determine the specific type of impairment they come with.

Screen children in schools and communities for impairment. All learners in SIEP pilot schools were screened annually to determine what impairment they might have. An interdisciplinary team composed of technicians in the areas of vision, hearing, mental health, and physiotherapy was provided by the CBC Health Services. This team

went to each SIEP pilot school and screened all learners. They also screened children in the surrounding communities who aren't yet going to school or who are not going to school although they have reached or are above school-going age. The intent first is to determine the status of each child in terms of impairment in SIEP pilot schools and then recommend or advise on what to do if need be. Many of the cases identified or suspected received referral notes to hospitals for further diagnosis. In the 2019/2020 school year, 3,486 learners (1,635 males and 1,851 females) were screened in and around SIEP pilot schools. In the 2020/2021 school year, 2,456 learners (1,145 males and 1,311 females) were screened in and around SIEP pilot schools. Table 1 shows the types of impairments identified in SIEP pilot schools for the 2020/2021 school year.

Table 1: Number of Learners with Impairments Enrolled in SIEP Pilot School for 2020/2021 Academic year (Screening done in January 2021)

Disability Type		BCHS Nkwen			Magba			Koutaba			Foumbot			Bafoussam			CBC Nkwen			GTot al
		M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T	
Visual Impairments	Blind	2	1	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	5
	Low Vision	3	2	5	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	8
Hearing and Speech Impairments	Deaf	2	4	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
	Hearing impairment	1 0	1 3	23	3	3	6	3	2	5	3	1	4	1	1	2	9	9	1 8	58
	Speech and/or Language disorder	4	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
Mobility Impairments	Cerebral Palsy	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	5	7	9	
	Club feet	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Hydrocephalus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Spina bifida	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Polio	1	2	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
	Knock or bow kneed	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Chronic Osteomyelitis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Amputation	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Muscular disease (neuromuscular disorder)	0	3	3	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
	Other movements	1	0	1	5	3	8	3	2	5	3	2	5	0	7	7	1	0	1	27
Dwarf	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	
Learning and/or	Cerebral Palsy	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	

Behavioural Problems	Autism Spectrum disorder	21	55	76	15	12	27	5	4	9	4	5	9	4	4	8	5	5	10	139
	Intellectual disability/ learning problem	7	7	14	0	0	0	2	1	3	1	2	3	1	1	2	1	4	5	27
	Mental retardation	0	0	0	1	1	2	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
	Down syndrome	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Epilepsy	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1
	Learning behavior	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	2
	ADHD	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cosmetic Problems	Albinism	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Burns	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cleft lip, plate	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Grand Total		54	88	142	26	19	45	14	12	26	11	12	23	9	13	22	19	24	43	301

After the screening process, the list of learners identified and confirmed with impairments is established school by school and class by class. Then, this is sent back to the school so that each teacher knows the learners in his or her class that needs attention and the type of attention. For example, a learner with vision impairment might need a preferential sitting position, then the teacher does provide that. In addition, a learner who has hearing challenges with one ear might be given another comfortable sitting position so that the functional ear might capture as much sound as possible. Furthermore, if a learner with impairment needs a buddy, that is also provided. Another advantage of sending the screening list back to the school is so that teachers do lesson preparation at home with these students in mind. Teachers ask questions to themselves during lesson preparation at home like, how do I support this learner with vision impairment understand the concept I am to teach? What activity can be enacted in class that has the potential to expose the concept I am about to teach these learner with impairments? and so on. We intend here that each teacher carefully think of their learners' understanding and how to engage and communicate with them during classroom enactment. In doing this and focusing on these learners with impairment, we believe other learners will benefit tremendously.

Provide conditional cash transfers to parents of children with disabilities. In addition to the 10% tuition fee waiver mentioned above, SIEP provided cash support (50,000 FCFA monthly) to some learners with disabilities for two years. Only 7 out of the 378 learners with impairments were selected to benefit from this cash support. The selection process was not easy. Many parameters were considered in achieving this. For these children to continue receiving this support for the two year period, they must be in school. If for some reason, they are away from school doing other things, they will forfeit this support. Community Based Rehabilitation (CBR) of the CBCHS visit these children regularly in their homes to ascertain good feeding and health conditions.

Undertake routine supervision. We undertook regular quarterly supervision in all SIEP pilot schools. The Education Adviser and Project Officer of SIEP were responsible for this. These visits were programmed to meet two goals. First, to follow up on each teacher in their practice as teachers having CWDs in their classrooms and second, to meet parents having CWDs attending the SIEP pilot school in particular.

Observing teachers. When we arrive at each of these schools on the week of school visits, we usually have a brief general meeting with the teaching staff. This meeting is intended to greet the staff, encourage them, and tell them we have come so that together, we learn from their practice. If challenges are noticed, we will discuss possible ways of overcoming them because we are into it together. We believe this will cause the teachers to feel relaxed and to function normally as they teach and we observe. This, we believe gives a sense of friendliness between the teachers and us.

During classroom observation, we do not offer a word. We allow the teacher to do his or her work to the end and we only take notes of things that are good that need to be reinforced, things that are challenging and could have been better otherwise, and things that the teacher needs to pay attention to. Another area of focus we consider critical is whether that classroom has CWDs and what impairments they have. How did the teacher include these learners in the lesson? Did the teacher think about them during lesson planning? What material options are there for the teacher to manage? How did the teacher manage these options within the class? Was it a success? What is responsible for the success? Did it fail? What happened? What modifications are possible to make it better? We usually observe a number of lessons and have post-lesson discussions during break periods when the teachers are less busy and sometimes after school when they are done with the work of the day.

After each lesson observed, we discuss among ourselves (SIEP Education Adviser and Project Officer), identify and agree on one or two critical things to focus on and then the teachers observed are invited for post-lesson discussions one after the other. We begin such a discussion by asking the teacher to tell us how the lesson went. At this point, we listen carefully to the teacher and then ask questions that push their thoughts further. If the critical things we think are important for sharing come up as the teacher makes their submission, then we can probe them further to critically think of ways the lesson can be made better. Otherwise, when we begin our presentation, the focus is on the positives that were observed and then we bring in areas that need improvements. After all the post-lesson observation discussions are done, a meeting with parents of the school having CWDs and the teachers of the school are called.

Meeting with parents having CWDs. For each child with disability, we invite both parents to attend these meetings. We do this because we believe both parents are in partnership to raise the child. Statistics show that some parents come together, some don't show up and for other children, only their mothers show up for the meetings. These meetings brought together 201 parents (29 Males and 172 Females) having CWDs. The aim of this meeting is so that parents having CWDs interact with teachers of the school as partners to support these learners. Now since the children are with their parents at home, some engagements create impact in the lives of the children at home and need to be continued at school. In school, there are some aspects that the children have found great success with that the parents need to know so that they follow up and continue supporting the children at home. When these parents meet with the teachers of their CWDs, sharing these ideas has removed frustrations for parents at home of what they thought wasn't working and on the teacher trying out things that work from home to also overcome their challenges at school.

Another important part of these meetings is the encouragement support that parents get from each other. Some parents are so discouraged that they see nothing good that their children with disabilities can offer. This discouragement can greatly affect the way the parents react to the children, producing further negative impacts on the child. On the other hand, some parents have been able to overcome those discouragements and are now on the success side. We noticed that when some parents vent their frustrations about a child with a disability they have, other parents were able to speak calmly, offering encouragement to their peers to cheer them up. We noticed that the discouraged parents always left our meetings very happy and promised to try out suggestions offered by other parents. We also noticed that in follow-up meetings, the attitude of the discouraged parents greatly shifted towards the positive axis. They can express love to their CWDs and are more ready to support them become successful.

We ensure that parents go home with a different notion of success. Success in Cameroon as well as in many other countries in the world has been defined exclusively in terms of academic certifications. However, we acknowledge that some of the CWDS might never really be able to have academic certificates in school. However, other forms of

success can be realized. For example, the child may come to school and be able to independently access and use toilet facilities. This is a great success and it frees parents whose lives were reduced to staying at home with the child because the CWD cannot take care of themselves. Some of these children can begin to bath and do other things that they could not do earlier, which is a success. In addition, although academic work is not their thing, they can learn an art which is a great success.

We found that this redefinition of success changed the perspectives of many of the parents having CWDs. They expressed happiness and committed themselves to making improvements in the way the children are handled. On the other hand some of the parents having CWDs invited to the meetings never show up. They have missed out on such opportunities to make the lives of their children better. We haven't given up on them. We will continue to find other avenues to reach out to them.

Creation/functioning of resource centre and rooms. Resource Centre (RC) and Resource Rooms (RM) are intended to help learners with impairment gain greater access to quality inclusive education. The resource centre has a lot of resources and assistive devices that could be used to support learners with impairments. The RC and RMs have braillists that are charged with the responsibility to Braille worksheets, examination questions, and some lesson notes for learners with vision impairments. The braillists are also responsible for training learners with vision impairments on how to braille using braille slates. Furthermore, the resource centre has American Sign Language (ASL) instructors who are responsible for following lessons in the different classes having learners with hearing impairments so they can interpret the lessons into signs for HI learners to understand.

In addition to these resources, the resource centre and resource room have assistive devices that are used to support learners with impairments. Some of these assistive devices at the RC and RMs include: Optima Go LED pocket magnifier (10), Okolux Plus LED Stand mag 4x/4 (7), Alum fold cane 110 cm (15), Alum fold cane 125 cm (15), Innus Interline Braille frame (8), Perkins Classic Brailier (1), Heavy Pickwick white 250gsm (50), White canes (20), Recorders (10), Slates (10), Styluses (20), Perkins Brailier(1), Braille papers (3000),Type writers (4), Magnifiers (10), Embosser (1), Computers (5), Abacus (10), photocopier, printer, raised diagrams, and other charts one the wall.

The resource centre is managed by a Coordinator who is an expert in special education. With the help of the coordinator, many support and services are offered at the resource centre. The resource centre organizes several capacity-building training workshops, seminars, and online classes for all stake holders (teachers and parents) in inclusive education practices. This has led to better classroom management and improved teaching methods. With the scarcity of ASL instructors, the resource centre has organized many training sessions to equip teachers with the knowledge and skills in ASL so that they can effectively communicate with the hearing impaired in their classrooms. Most parents having hearing-impaired children do communicate with them using non-standard signs. So, the resource centre has also organized ASL training sessions with these parents so that the communication at home is similar to that in school to avoid confusion in the studies of HI learners. In some of our SIEP pilot schools (CBC Primary School Nkwen and BCHS Nkwen), every Thursday of the week and for 30 minutes, the entire school is trained in ASL, from basics to complex signing. This is so that the other children acquire ASL skills and are able to interact with their HI peers during group work activities in class and other school activities.

Also, the resource centre runs preschool programs for children with severe to profound vision and hearing impairments. The vision-impaired learners receive training in braille, mobility and orientation, while the hearing-impaired learners are taught the standard ASL; for their eventual inclusion into mainstream classrooms. The resource centre also has pull-out sessions for learners with impairments in the resource rooms for direct specialized instruction and academic remediation. These learners receive one-on-one, small group and remedial teachings depending on their individual needs. In addition, the resource centre also develops Individual education plans (IEPs) to support all learners with severe to profound impairments. This is also to help teachers and parents monitor and track learners' progress against their individual learning goals.

Outcomes

With all the above put together, what do we get? The outcome will be presented here in two parts. First, I will present the academic achievements of each school and secondly, I will provide success stories as presented by some parents and care givers. Table 2 provides the overall results of the schools from the 2018/2019, 2019/2020, and 2020/2021 academic years. There is an overall increase in academic performance from the academic year to 2020/2021 academic years. This might imply that a focus on IE, with the different disabilities in mind makes teaching even very explicit to learners without impairments. In addition to the normal classroom examination results mentioned in Table 2, some CWDs do register for end-of-year certificate examinations.

Table 2: Overall average of each school for three academic years

	Annual Average for 2018/2019	Annual Average for 2019/2020	Annual Average for 2020/2021
CBC School Magba	12.83	12.82	17.18
CBC School Koutaba	14.68	16.09	18.64
CBC School Foubot	10.95	15.50	15.50
CBC School Bafoussam	11.20	12.00	12.69
CBC School Nkwen	11.07	12.69	12.85
BCHS Nkwen	09.68	10.70	11.04

Table 3 below shows the number sat and the number passed from year to year as well as the type of impairments that the candidates had. It is worth noting that the First School Leaving Certificate (FSLC) Examination is written at the end of primary school education, the General Certificate of Education (GCE) Examination, Ordinary Level, is written at the end of five years in secondary school and the General Certificate of Education (GCE) Examination, Advanced Level is written at the end of two years in high school. The General Certificate of Education (GCE) Examination, Advanced Level ushers the learners into university studies.

The results in Table 3 reveal that our piloting of IE can give hope to CWDs to be successful at certificate examinations. It also reveals that there is still more to be done to encourage CWDs to succeed in schools. However, the success we register is not only in academic certification. Some of our successes can be seen in areas like developing positive self-esteem as illustrated in the two success stories below.

Table 3: Success of CWDs at End of year Certificate Examinations

First School Leaving Certificate (FSLC) Examination			
Year	No Sat	No Passed	Type of impairment
2018/2019	0	0	
2019/2020	3	2	Profound speech and hearing loss, profound vision loss
2020/2021	5	1	Profound speech and hearing loss
2021/2022	4	3	All profound speech and hearing loss

GCE Ordinary Level			
Year	No Sat	No Passed	Type of impairment
2018/2019	2	1	Severe vision loss
2019/2020	2	1	Severe vision loss
2020/2021	2	0	
2021/2022	5	2	Profound speech and hearing loss (Commercial/ grammar)

GCE Advanced Level			
---------------------------	--	--	--

Year	No Sat	No Passed	Type of impairment
2018/2019	0	0	
2019/2020	0	0	
2020/2021	1	1	Severe vision loss
2021/2022	1	1	Profound Orthopaedic impairment (Cerebral Palsy)

Success Stories

For each of the stories below, we present the learner before and after coming to our pilot schools. All the names presented here are pseudonyms to protect the learner's identity.

JIMKA. Jimka, a female, is 14 years old. She is an internally displaced pupil in class 6 who has multiple disabilities (mild intellectual disability, epilepsy, and rickets), which impacts her ability to learn effectively. Nevertheless, Jimka can learn, to read, and to write and carryout a number of activities. Jimka has had frequent seizures since the age of 2 and is on medications since then. She has also had surgeries on her legs to straighten her curved legs and has worn calipers from when she was in nursery school till class 2. She is on medication for Epilepsy. Her mother said they heard about the SIEP program on the radio and a person with a disability also reported that they could be helped at CBC Primary School Nkwen, Bamenda. So, they enrolled her and she resumed schooling after some time of being at home. Her mother reports that before coming to CBC Nkwen, she acted up at times and threw tantrums frequently when she was angry. This is probably due to the frustrations of her impairments. She added that Jimka was mixing up information, she was a slow learner, walked slowly, and writes anywhere in her book with no coherence. She refuses to read even when asked to do so by the teacher. She hated school because she was falling behind in academics and also because of her epilepsy which is socially isolating. She was not taking her medications regularly and was delinquent with medication sometimes for as long as 2 months.

Jimka's mother went further to say that since they enrolled her at CBC School Nkwen, the story has been different. She, the mother was educated on her role in helping Jimka succeed in school. The inclusive education teacher took time to explain her responsibilities and what they would do at school. Jimka's mother added that for 2 years now, the interventions received at CBC Nkwen have really helped Jimka mitigate her impairments and enable her to learn. According to Jimka's mother, Jimka has benefited from the following interventions to include her in-class activities: frequent reminders to copy notes well; one-on-one attention during independent work and remedial lessons in the resource room, extended time to copy notes, and that she has been called and reminded to order for Jimka's medications. Jimka's mother went on to say Jimka is now in Class 6 with much improvement in her health (no more seizures in school) and academics and looking forward to writing the First School Leaving Certificate Examinations, a thing they never dreamt could happen.

One of Jimka's neighbors in Ghana street where she lives and who knows her expressed amazement that Jimka is still in school and that she has fewer seizures and is now so confident in herself. She said they are seeing a new Jimka. Jimka's mother ended by saying she was so proud of her and was hopeful she would have a fulfilled life.

PILATE. Pilate is male and 11 years old. He was born with cerebral palsy. This seems to affect his physical functioning more; his limbs are frail and he uses a wheel chair. His fine motor abilities are limited too as he can barely hold a pencil to write. His intellect is not affected though; he is very intelligent. Pilate lacks muscle control and that affects his ability to maintain balance and posture. He also has many other health and developmental problems as seen in his inability to speak clearly, walk, and sit well. With all these impairments, Pilate's academic performance is limited. Due to frustration (limitations due to his disability, not going to school, staying home just with his grandmother, etc.), he would throw tantrums when he is angry. His grandmother who takes care of him said she was informed by a neighbour who listened to a radio program in which SIEP activities were highlighted to take him to CBC Primary school, Nkwen. His grandmother attested that Pilate's spirits were low until he came to CBC Nkwen from another school that engaged him only in weaving baskets which he did not like.

She said since coming to CBC Primary School, Nkwen with all the inclusion support from classroom teachers, resource room support staff, other teachers, peers, grandmother, and driver; after four months in school, Pilate has made some progress academically and socially, especially his self-esteem. According to his grandmother, Pilate is so happy at CBC Primary School Nkwen and recounts that he loves his school so much because he is learning in the classroom, has many friends, and everyone loves him. Pilate's grandmother added that all these have in turn boosted his self-esteem and he now has a positive view of life. Pilate is confident that despite his disability, he will marry, have children, take care of his grandmother be an educated business man, own a car, and even buy cars for his teachers. I am so elated, said the grandmother and told the staff "only God will reward you." She said, "I am happy because my grandson is happy." The taxi driver who brings Pilate to school said "I am marveled seeing him beam with joy and excitement whenever I drop him off in school." The driver reports that Pilate tells him "I am very happy going to school every day."

Next Steps and Challenges

Our first step is to ensure that all schools of the Cameroon Baptist Convention Education Department go inclusive. Our second next step is to involve other confessional schools in Cameroon. We have already received a letter from the Education Secretary of the Presbyterian Church in Cameroon (PCC) expressing the urgent need for their schools to go inclusive. He expressed that their schools have many children with special needs but because of lack of experience and capacity to handle them, they are turned away. Those who are granted admission aren't receiving the desired attention. They struggle and dropout. Our third next step is to involve privately owned schools in making their schools inclusive.

All of the steps mentioned above will require training of personnel, monitoring the practice of teaching in all schools involved to include all learners, and remodeling school infrastructures to accommodate all Children With Disabilities (CWD). Our greatest challenge is the availability of funds to effectively carry out these activities. We therefore advocate and solicit for funding partner organizations to accompany us as we scale up towards the realization of subsequent phases of our Sustainable Inclusive Education Project (SIEP). We are also in dire need of human resources such as experts in various aspects of Inclusive Education to partner with us to attain the above-mentioned steps.

Conclusion

It has been a worthwhile experience engaging all learners in SIEP pilot schools. We have learned much and there is still much to learn. This is because each child is unique and although two children might have the same disability, their uniqueness brings in specificities that make each case different. So, one-to-one monitoring gives us the opportunity to deal with each child differently and measures each child's progress against their previous competences. In Matthew 9: 37, Jesus said to his disciples, "The harvest is plentiful but the workers are few" (NIV). Although Jesus Christ said this in relation to people in urgent need of the gospel to be saved, this statement is very true in the case of inclusive education as well. Many children with disabilities do not yet have access to quality inclusive education. In many of the schools that attempt to accommodate CWDs, the staff are overwhelmed because of the huge numbers and just a few of them. We are in need of qualified, knowledgeable, dedicated and committed staff so that these CWDs get adequate support to thrive in mainstream classrooms.

References

- Cameroon Baptist Convention Health Services. cbhealthservices.org
- The Holy Bible, New International Version
- United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (2015). https://www.icevirtuallibrary.com/page/ice-news/sdgs?gclid=Cj0KQCQiAmaibBhCAARIsAKUlaKSidDyiZ1JAeayx7o--dErgw0iDHCxbHtOKsD4DlkdUgc18i0JJdiUaAs0sEALw_wcB